

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF AUDIO-ASSISTED REPEATED READING (AARR) AND PEER-MEDIATED READING (PMR) IN ENHANCING THE ORAL READING FLUENCY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Oral reading fluency (ORF) is essential in developing learners' decoding skills, enhancing reading comprehension, and preparing them for academic success. This quasi-experimental study aimed to determine the more effective strategy between audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) and peer-mediated reading (PMR) in improving the ORF of senior high school students. Conducted in a public senior high school in Misamis Oriental during the 2024–2025 academic year, the study involved 60 students identified through their ORF profiles using the Department of Education's PHIL-IRI (2018) tool. Over an eight-week intervention period, participants were assigned to either the AARR or PMR group. The study employed descriptive statistics, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and ANCOVA to evaluate the strategies' effectiveness before and after the interventions. Results indicated that both AARR and PMR significantly improved learners' oral reading fluency in terms of accuracy and comprehension. However, audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) demonstrated greater effectiveness. These findings affirm that both strategies contribute to improved ORF and can support academic achievement among senior high school learners. It is recommended that future research examine the long-term effects of combining AARR and PMR in blended or technology-assisted learning environments to support differentiated instruction and sustained fluency development.

Keywords: *oral reading fluency, audio-assisted repeated reading, peer-mediated reading*

INTRODUCTION

Oral English proficiency, particularly through oral reading fluency, plays a vital role in strengthening learners' ability to decode text accurately and read with expression and comprehension across content areas (Duffy et al., 2024). As learners develop fluency—marked by accuracy, appropriate rate, and prosody—they begin to read with meaning, confidence, and independence (Gedik & Akyol, 2022; Daley et al., 2020). Frameworks such as the National Reading Panel (2000) and the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI, 2018) reinforce the role of oral reading fluency (ORF) as a core competency for academic achievement.

However, despite this well-established importance, national assessments continue to indicate that many senior high school students in the Philippines fall below fluency benchmarks, leading to comprehension difficulties and reduced academic performance. These challenges are more pronounced in learners who are still developing English as a second language, limiting their ability to succeed in reading-dependent tasks across disciplines.

Various instructional approaches have been shown to support the development of oral reading fluency, particularly audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) and peer-mediated reading (PMR). These evidence-based strategies enhance fluency through scaffolded repetition, auditory modeling, and peer support, helping learners build automaticity and comprehension skills (Chang, 2024; Oshokoya, 2023; Cockerill et al., 2023). Yet, limited research explores their application among senior high school learners, particularly within the Philippine public-school context. Existing studies have largely focused on younger or early-grade learners, leaving a gap in understanding how these methods can be adapted to meet older students' cognitive, linguistic, and motivational needs.

Moreover, studies rarely examine the comparative effectiveness of these strategies in classrooms where English is not the first language, nor do they connect these literacy interventions to broader developmental goals. Addressing these gaps, this study contributes to Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) by promoting inclusive and equitable reading instruction, and to SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) by supporting literacy interventions for learners at risk of academic underperformance. Through a targeted reading intervention using AARR and PMR, this research aims to improve learners' oral English proficiency and promote equitable access to academic success.

Framework

This study is grounded on the premise that two instructional strategies—audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) and peer-mediated reading (PMR)—can significantly enhance the oral reading fluency (ORF) of senior high school students. Oral reading fluency, which comprises accuracy and reading comprehension, is fundamental to literacy development and academic performance. Drawing from LaBerge and Samuels' (1974) Automaticity Theory, the study assumes that through repeated and modeled practice, learners can

decode words effortlessly, thereby freeing cognitive resources for higher-order comprehension tasks. The AARR strategy builds on this principle by exposing learners to repeated passages accompanied by audio models. This auditory input reinforces word recognition, intonation, and pacing, enabling learners to internalize fluent reading patterns and build automaticity over time (Canuto et al., 2024; Syahriani et al., 2022). Within this strategy, teacher scaffolding in the form of corrective feedback and demonstration plays a crucial role, especially for students performing at the instructional or frustration level in reading.

Vygotsky's concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) states that learners can perform tasks with the help of a more knowledgeable other. This aligns with teacher-led audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR), where the teacher provides scaffolding, such as modeling fluent reading and offering corrective feedback, to support learners' reading progress (Kushki & Nassaji, 2024). Vygotsky's sociocultural theory holds that learning occurs through both intrapersonal and interpersonal interactions. Learners internalize new knowledge through language and shared activities, which supports the inclusion of audio-assisted reading in the study. By listening to teacher-recorded passages, learners are guided in recognizing correct pronunciation, pacing, and expression (Asrimawati & Margana, 2020; Syahriani et al., 2022). Audio-assisted reading allows students to experience interactive feedback and build fluency through auditory input.

Moreover, with repeated reading (RR), *audio-assisted extensive reading (AAR)* provides a new learning environment that helps learners "recognize the letter-sound relationship. Students who use audio-assisted reading find it easier to concentrate. Through this technique, the voice or audio recording of the teacher's voice is utilized to let the learner listen to how the teacher reads the passage at an accurate pace (Hekleman, 1969) as cited in Syahriani et al. (2022). In the present study, audio-assisted reading (AAR) is integrated with repeated reading (RR) to aid the participants during their reading practice.

Peer-Mediated Reading (PMR) is likewise rooted in Vygotsky's sociocultural theory. It emphasizes collaborative learning where learners co-construct understanding through social interaction (Al-Buraiki, 2023). During Peer-Mediated Reading (PMR) sessions, learners take turns reading aloud, discussing ideas from the text, and providing peer feedback—activities that foster fluency and engagement (Alkhudiry, 2022). In this study, Peer-Mediated Reading (PMR) served as the control group strategy and was assessed for its effectiveness in improving oral reading fluency.

The conceptual framework of this study further guided the intervention process by focusing on the interrelationship between the components of oral reading fluency: accuracy and reading comprehension. These components provide a lens through which the effectiveness of each strategy is assessed. Accuracy refers to learners' ability to decode and pronounce words correctly (Saha et al., 2021). *Accuracy* is a key foundation for overall reading proficiency and comprehension (Lee & Stoodley, 2024; Rafanan & Raymundo, 2024); this is determined by correct word recognition with minimal errors (Kasimba, 2024). Reading comprehension is assessed through the learners' ability to answer comprehension questions after oral reading (Pillaga Riofrío, 2024). *Reading*

comprehension reflects the ability to make meaning from the text (Arsyta, 2024; Sultana et al., 2024). These components were enhanced through the implementation audio audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR), and peer-mediated reading (PMR).

Repeated Reading (RR) involves rereading passages until fluency goals are reached (Samuels, 1979), and Audio-Assisted Reading provides listening models that guide students' practice (Heckelman, 1969, as Syahrani et al., 2022). Meanwhile, peer-mediated reading (PMR) incorporates strategies like partner reading, choral reading, and paragraph shrinking to promote collaborative reading (Cockerill et al., 2023; Leite et al., 2024).

On the other hand, *Peer Mediation Reading (PMR)* is a strategy that includes peers' encouraging environment as they engage in collaborative learning activities (Leite et al., 2024); these involve students working together to reach a common objective in learning (Cockerill et al., 2023). The Peer Mediated Reading (PMR) strategy was assigned to the control group, and the reading activities embedded with these strategies are partner reading, choral reading, and paragraph shrinking.

These variables are summarized and visually presented in the study's conceptual framework, shown in Figure 1, which illustrates the relationships of the independent variables (strategies employed) and the dependent variable (Oral Reading Fluency).

Figure 1: Schematic Presentation of the Study

Objective of the Study

This study attempted to determine which of these strategies: audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR), and peer-mediated reading (PMR), is more effective in improving the oral reading fluency of senior high school students.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine which of these strategies is more effective in improving the oral reading fluency of senior high school students.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. How do the participants in each group perform in their oral reading fluency before and after the interventions considering:
 - 1.1. accuracy; and
 - 1.2. reading comprehension?
2. How do the participants in each group compare their oral reading fluency before and after the interventions?
3. Which of these strategies is more effective in improving the oral reading fluency of the participants?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quasi-experimental design to compare the effectiveness of audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) and peer-mediated reading (PMR) in improving the oral reading fluency (ORF) of senior high school students. Sixty Grade 11 learners from a public school in Misamis Oriental were selected based on their ORF levels using the Department of Education's Phil-IRI Manual (2018). AARR and PMR served as the independent variables, while ORF scores, measured in terms of accuracy and reading comprehension, were the dependent variables. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize learners' performance before and after the intervention, while the Wilcoxon signed-rank test assessed the significance of score improvements within each group. To identify the more effective strategy while adjusting for pre-test differences, an Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted, offering a clearer comparison of the instructional interventions' impact on learners' ORF outcomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: How do the participants in each group perform in their oral reading fluency (ORF) before and after the interventions considering: 1.1. accuracy; and 1.2. reading comprehension?

Table 1 shows the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' oral reading fluency (ORF) in terms of accuracy before and after the interventions. In the experimental group (AARR), pre-test results revealed that 56.67% of the learners were at the frustration level and 43.33% were at the instructional level, with none achieving the independent level. Following the intervention, there was a notable shift: 40.0% reached the independent level, and 60.0% moved to the instructional level, with no learners remaining in the frustration category. The group's mean score improved from 89% (frustration level) to 95% (instructional level), indicating a substantial gain in decoding accuracy.

In contrast, the control group (PMR) showed limited improvement. Although learners also transitioned out of the frustration level by post-test, the majority remained at the instructional level (60.0%), and only 40.0% reached the independent level. The group's mean score increased only marginally from 88% to 89%, remaining within the frustration level.

These results indicate that while both AARR and PMR strategies increased the learners' reading accuracy, audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR had higher movement. The clear shift from frustration to instructional and independent levels among the experimental group supports previous findings that AARR, through repeated exposure and auditory modeling, strengthens word recognition and decoding accuracy (Canuto et al., 2024; Damra et al., 2025).

Table 1

Frequency, and Percentage Distribution of Participants' Oral Reading Fluency (ORF) before and after the Interventions (Accuracy)

Range	Interpretation	AUDIO ASSISTED REPEATED READING				PEER-MEDIATED READING			
		Pretest		Post Test		Pretest		Post Test	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
97-100%	Independent	0	0.0	12	40.0	0	0.0	12	40.0
90-96%	Instructional	13	43.33	18	60.0	11	36.67	18	60.0
89% and below	Frustration	17	56.67	0	0.0	19	63.33	0	0.0
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0	30	100.0	30	100.0

Mean	89%	95%	88%	89%
Interpretation	Frustration	Instructional	Frustration	Frustration
SD	2.10	2.0	2.10	2.23

Table 2 shows that in the experimental group (AARR), 66.67% of learners were initially at the frustration level and 33.33% at the instructional level, with none achieving independence. After the intervention, 50.0% progressed to the independent level, and the remaining 50.0% reached the instructional level, with no learners remaining in the frustration category. The mean score increased markedly from 43% to 76%, reflecting a significant improvement in comprehension.

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participants' Oral Reading Fluency Before and after the Interventions (Reading Comprehension)

Range	Interpretation	AUDIO ASSISTED REPEATED READING				PEER-MEDIATED READING			
		Pretest		Post Test		Pretest		Post Test	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
80-100%	Independent	0	0.0	15	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
59-79%	Instructional	10	33.33	15	50.0	10	33.33	10	33.33
58% & below	Frustration	20	66.67	0	0.0	20	66.67	20	66.67
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0	30	100.0	30	100.0
Mean		43%		76%		43%		48%	
Interpretation		Frustration		Instructional		Frustration		Frustration	
SD		15.0		11.0		14.42		12.23	

Conversely, the control group (PMR) showed minimal progress. The majority of learners (66.67%) remained at the frustration level from pre-test to post-test, with 33.33% at the instructional level, and no learners advancing to independence. The group's mean score rose only slightly from 43% to 48%, indicating limited improvement in comprehension skills.

These findings demonstrate that audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) substantially enhanced learners' reading comprehension, consistent with previous research showing that auditory modeling combined with repeated reading supports both decoding and meaning-making (Caabay et al., 2024; Widiastuti, 2025). In contrast, peer-mediated reading (PMR) had minimal effect on comprehension outcomes.

Research Question 2: How do the participants in each group compare their oral reading fluency (accuracy and reading comprehension) before and after the interventions?

Ho₁. There is no significant difference in each of the groups' oral reading fluency before and after the interventions.

Table 3 presents the results of the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test comparing participants' oral reading fluency (ORF), in terms of accuracy and reading comprehension, before and after the interventions. The findings indicate statistically significant improvements in both groups, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This confirms that both audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) and peer-mediated reading (PMR) were effective in enhancing learners' oral reading fluency.

In the AARR group, all 30 participants showed higher post-test scores in accuracy (positive ranks = 30; Z = 4.78, p < .001), and 28 of them showed improvements in reading comprehension (Z = 4.66, p < .001), with only 2 maintaining the same scores. Likewise, in the PMR group, 21 participants recorded gains in accuracy, while 6 had lower scores and 3 remained the same (Z = 3.85, p < .001). For reading comprehension, 13 participants improved, while 17 had no change (Z = 3.50, p < .001). These results denote that both strategies significantly supported learners' fluency development across the two measured components.

Table 3

Result of the Test of Difference in the Participants' Oral Reading Fluency (Accuracy and Comprehension) before and after the Interventions

	AUDIO ASSISTED REPEATED READING					PEER-MEDIATED READING				
	Nega-tive Ranks	Posi-tive Ranks	Tie s	Z	p	Neg a-tive Ranks	Posi-tive Ranks	Tie s	Z	p
Accuracy	0	30	0	4.78*	<.001	6	21	3	3.85**	<.001

Reading Comprehen sion	0	28	2	4.66* *	<.001	0	13	17	3.50**	<.001
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Legend: *Negative Ranks: Post test < Pretest* *Positive Ranks: Post test > Pretest*
Ties: Post test = Pretest

The findings are consistent with previous studies confirming that structured and interactive reading interventions can significantly enhance fluency outcomes. Wang et al. (2024) emphasized the value of repeated auditory modeling in improving decoding accuracy and rhythm, while Wijayanti (2024) and Yulianto et al. (2024) found that there were measurable gains in reading comprehension following guided peer reading and audio-based fluency programs in second-language settings. Both strategies applied in the current study offered meaningful learning opportunities: AARR through auditory input and repetition, and PMR through collaboration and peer engagement.

The comparable pre-test scores between the groups validate that improvements can be attributed to the interventions. These results affirm that both AARR and PMR are viable strategies for enhancing oral reading fluency among senior high school learners, particularly in contexts where foundational reading skills need reinforcement.

Research Question 3: Which of these strategies is more effective in improving the oral reading fluency of the participants?

Ho₂. None of the strategies is more effective in improving the oral reading fluency of the participants in terms of accuracy.

Ho₃. None of the strategies is more effective in improving the oral reading fluency of the participants in terms of reading comprehension.

A one-way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to examine the effect of the interventions on post-accuracy scores, controlling the pretest accuracy. After adjusting for pretests in accuracy (which served as the covariate), findings reveal a statistically significant difference between groups, $F(1,56) = 565.51$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .908$, indicating a strong effect size. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying that the audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) intervention is more helpful in enhancing oral reading fluency in the accuracy dimension (M=95.41) than the peer-mediated strategy (M=89.10).

Similarly, in reading comprehension, a one-way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to examine the effect of the interventions on post-reading comprehension scores, and control for the pretest. After adjusting for pretests in reading comprehension (which served as the covariate), findings reveal a statistically significant difference between groups, $F(1,56) = 143.47$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .716$, indicating a strong effect size. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying that the audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) intervention is more effective in enhancing oral reading fluency in the reading comprehension dimension (M=95.41) than the peer-mediated strategy (M=89.10).

Table 4*Analysis of Covariance on the Effect of the Interventions on the Participants' Oral Reading**Fluency*

Components of Oral Reading Fluency	Repeated Reading Group	Peer-Mediated Group	F(1, 56)	p	Partial Eta Squared
Accuracy	M = 95.41	M = 89.10	565.51	< .001	.908
Reading Comprehension	M = 76.10	M = 48.09	143.47	< .001	.716

Hence, the audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) strategy in the experimental group was more effective than the peer-mediated reading (PMR) in improving the accuracy of learner participants. This demonstrated that audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) is effective in enhancing learners' reading accuracy (Li, Avendaño, & Bak, 2024; Jose, 2024).

This finding indicates that, similar to reading accuracy, the treatment applied to the experimental group—audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR)—was significantly more effective in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of the learner participants compared to the peer-mediated reading (PMR) strategy used in the control group. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, as the AARR intervention yielded a statistically significant improvement in the participants' oral reading fluency (ORF).

In this line, audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) improves the reading comprehension skills of the learner participants. This stresses that audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) has enhanced the reading comprehension skills of the learners. Instead of taking the time to decode the words, this makes the learners focus on making meaning to grasp the message and content of the text (Liu, & Saad, 2025). Moreover, audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) enables the learner to easily understand the unpracticed passages (Park, 2022); (Widiastuti, 2025).

Thus, as shown in the statistical result in terms of oral reading fluency (ORF) (accuracy and reading comprehension) the audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) strategy applied in the experimental group was generally revealed to be a more effective intervention in improving the oral reading fluency (ORF) of the learner participants compared to that of the peer-mediated reading (PMR) in the control group.

Conclusions

The findings of this study confirmed that the research objective was successfully achieved. Both the experimental and control groups demonstrated significant improvements in oral reading fluency (ORF), supporting the effectiveness of audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) and peer-mediated reading (PMR) as instructional strategies. The outcomes affirm the theoretical foundations of the study, particularly the roles of automaticity, accuracy, and comprehension in developing oral reading proficiency through evidence-based interventions.

Moreover, the consistent gains among learners who received the AARR intervention highlight the value of repeated, scaffolded reading practice in addressing reading difficulties. These results underscore the importance of integrating structured reading programs into literacy instruction. The study contributes to existing literature and provides practical insights for curriculum developers and educators to adopt research-based interventions that support struggling readers, thereby advancing literacy outcomes in the senior high school context.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. *Instructional Institutions*, specifically in public senior high schools, may integrate audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) as part of the reading intervention programs and language classes to address the oral reading fluency (ORF) problems of the learners.
2. *Language Educators* may incorporate audio-assisted repeated reading (AARR) integrated with peer-mediated reading (PMR) fostering not only collaboration among students but also promoting learner-centered instruction. Reading intervention pieces of training and workshops may be conducted to equip teachers with research-based reading strategies for them to be embedded in the classroom setting.
3. *Future researchers* may consider conducting a qualitative study that involves direct observation of learners' reading behaviors to provide deeper insights into the effectiveness of Audio-Assisted Repeated Reading (AARR) and Peer-Mediated Reading (PMR) strategies in enhancing the oral reading fluency of senior high school students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards, securing informed consent from both the learners and their parents or guardians, ensuring that participants were fully aware of the study's objectives, procedures, benefits, and risks and that their involvement was entirely voluntary with the freedom to withdraw at any time without any consequences. The anonymity and

confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained through secure data storage and controlled access to records. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded by implementing a supportive, non-judgmental environment and continuous monitoring to address any emotional or psychological discomfort. The researchers affirm that no conflict of interest exists in this study, plagiarism was rigorously avoided, and the interpretation of findings was conducted impartially. Furthermore, the results were used solely for research purposes to contribute to the understanding and improvement of oral reading fluency among senior high school learners.

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